
A Review of the Barriers to the Nigeria's Developmental Aspirations and the Socio- Philosophical Ways Forward

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ABSTRACT

Development is assumed to be a predictor of whether or not a country is developing. Despite its multitude of people, natural, and material resources, a critical examination of Nigeria's developmental projections indicates that the country has failed to meet the aspirations of its population. The goal of this research was to identify Nigeria's development problems. This paper used a qualitative research approach and textual analysis to argue that there still exist a wide gap in Nigeria's efforts to promote development because of various existential problems that has continued to present significant dangers to her development. These setbacks include, among others, include lack of adequate human resources to pursue and fulfill Nigeria's developmental plans and policies, corruption, and a lack of visionary administration. This paper concluded that if some of these identified impediments are addressed, Nigeria will experience national development.

Keywords: Development, Corruption, State of Infrastructure, Role of Philosophy.

INTRODUCTION

Many scholars have expressed different views on the definition and nature of the concept of development. "Development", is interpreted by scholars from two perspectives. Firstly, from economic perspective and also as a multi-dimensional notion that goes beyond pure economics. Economic growth accumulates and expands a country's industrial and financial capital which is measured by the gross national product and value (Meier, 1988). The United Nations Millennium

Development Goal (MDG's) are a set of goals that member state have agreed to achieved by the 2015 and become prominent in Nigeria's current development discourse.

The global mobilization behind the Millennium Development Goals has produced the most successful anti-poverty movement in history. The landmark commitment entered into by world leaders in the year 2000—to "spare no effort to free our fellow men, women and children from the abject and dehumanizing conditions of extreme poverty"—was translated into an inspiring framework of eight goals and, then, into wide-ranging practical steps that have enabled people across the world to improve their lives and their future prospects. The MDGs helped to lift more than one billion people out of extreme poverty, to make inroads against hunger, to enable more girls to attend school than ever before and to protect our planet. They generated new and innovative partnerships, galvanized public opinion and showed the immense value of setting ambitious goals. By putting people and their immediate needs at the forefront, the MDGs reshaped decision-making in developed and developing countries alike.

Statement of Problem and Objective of Study

This study aims to demonstrate that Nigeria still faces different barriers to national development. This submission corroborates several studies carried out by various scholars (Makinde, 2005; 2005; Babawale, 2007; Nnabuiife, 2010; Yunusa, 2009; itah, 2012; Gberevbie, Shodipo & oviasogie, 2013). Makinde (2005) examined some of the major barriers to Nigeria's development ranging from the imposition of policies on citizens, a shortage of sufficient human resources or capital

to carry our development plants and policies, corruption, and a shortage of trustworthy and visionary leadership.

Makinde (2005) further observed that developing countries policies are majorly imposed on the population without accommodation their interest and the populace are denied the possibility to take part I the provision of policies that will cater for their well-being. Statistics shows that Nigeria is ranked 152nd out of 187 countries in the Human Development program (UNDP) in 2014 showed that Nigeria's HDI is 0.381, which falls for below the global average. As a consequence a new administration inherits a lack of continuity and consistency in policy implementation when it takes office. Similarly, Dike (2010) also refers to "Leadership" as a hindrance to national development in Nigeria. He further submits that many individuals in positions of authority are not aware that leadership requires taking responsibility for critical issues. Inefficient Leadership is identified as a shortage of effective oversight and protocols for monitory the conduct of government officials and institutions. Eventually, politics is now a "do or die" affair, with ethical politics taking a backseat.

Literature Review

From the above explanation, we may argue that "philosophy" has a critical and intellectual discipline, has much to do with the development and growth of any country in the world. Generally speaking, mankind or human-beings are complex social beings in the universe because human beings constantly question, interrogate and probe various issues connected to their existence. By constantly engaging himself in "mental speculations" and asking basic questions that touches the heart

of his own existence, it could be argued that "rational thinking" and "philosophizing" began with the human person.

Therefore, the development of human critical mental capability for evaluating situations, trends and events is one major contribution that philosophy has assisted man to develop over the centuries. Another important area of 'development' of the human personality is "moral development". Therefore, moral development and maturity on the part of the citizens of any country represents "a pre-condition for the overall development" of such a country because there can be no serious development in any country if the citizens are morally bankrupt or undeveloped. Therefore, far from being irrelevant to the practical human experience and existence philosophy as an academic discipline represent one of the most powerful intellectual forces that are continue to shape human values, character, attitude and the various structure of human society. Thirwall (2008) noted that Nigeria is one of the world's impoverished nations faced with a critical challenge of lifting the economic and social status of the present-day global civilization. About one billion individuals out of over six billion experience extreme poverty, malnourishment, lack access to education, healthcare, and safe drinking water. This appalling situation is common in developing countries including Nigeria.

Oyedele (2012) noted for example that the state of infrastructure facilities in Nigeria is globally considered inadequate and it is a key fact that contributes to a dysfunctional society. In a democratic nation, infrastructure development serves as a crucial metric for assessing the success of democratic leaders and a basic pillar of studying democratic governance. Particularly, Nigeria has a higher

demand for infrastructural development than she was in the grip military dictatorship. As a result of the regular dearth of infrastructural resources emanating from higher intangible gaps in budgetary provisions Nigeria has continue to remain in the backwaters of underdevelopment.

The present state of infrastructure in Nigeria is deteriorating; and urgently massive rehabilitation, repair reconstruction across the country. Currently, the required political, will and vision to tackle this infrastructural challenges are clearly absent. Government acts as the framework saddled with the responsibilities of planning, organization, governing, and overseeing individuals living in a specific region to give a comfortable living environment and promote a sense of belonging. The power to implement any measures to create an environment that promotes the well-being of all citizens' rest on government. In addition, Nigeria is one of the underdeveloped countries whose infrastructure development poses challenges because of limited access to government, necessitating the identification of appropriate projects, performing feasibility and viability assessments, and commencing physical development. Other obstacles that needed to be resolved include the provision of finance to undertake massive infrastructural overhaul across the country, introduction of technological backed solutions to supply, maintain and sustain regular power supply to Nigeria's industrial and manufacturing sectors as well as accessible to all citizens.

Source: ICRC, 2017

This picture reflect appropriately the road network that the Nigerian State parades in recent times

Figure 1

The Factors that Serve as Catalysts for Corrupt Practice in Nigeria

According to CLEEN foundation (2010), the factors that have contributed to Nigeria's culture of corruption and lack of accountability are as follows:

Problem of Impunity and Poor Leadership

The common belief among Nigerians is that politics provides a fast access to wealth. This is evident in those in position of power and this shows their highest level of corruption practices among those who had faced investigations for corrupt practices in both past and present are State Governors and Local Government Chairman. These categories of people get the share of their corruption from overpriced contracts, diversion of funds that are intended for public organization or sectors into their personal or overseas accounts through

laundering. This corrupt practices has made the general populace to see this as either legal or illegal way of acquiring wealth.

Underfunding of Anti-Corruption Agencies in Nigeria

The agencies saddled with the responsibility of fighting high-tech crime, corporate misconduct, and bureaucratic malpractices need sufficient resources and funding. Regrettably, Nigeria has not made adequate provisions and funding to combat corruption and this has made many anti-corruption organizations reporting insufficient financial resources to carry-out their important missions.

Inadequate Database

The shortage of a comprehensive citizen database in Nigeria is a hindrance to criminal investigations and limitation of sharing information with international counterparts. If there is accurate records maintenance, criminal activities can be effectively prevented.

Lack of Reforms

Corruption can be prevented in Nigeria by reforming the public sector. Here, accounting for over half of Nigerian's corruption cases will be a crucial step towards combating corruption in the country. Long-term reforms in public institutions (that is, Civil Service and Judiciary) can lessen corruption in Nigeria.

Lack of National Integration

One hindrance to prevent corruption in Nigeria is lack of national integration. Nigeria is a country with multiple cultures. Nigerians therefore, are divided along ethnicity, tribalism, socio-economy and religion. Consequently, cases of corruption

are grouped based on ethnicity, tribe, or religion and every government appointment is seen as a chance to take part in the national cake. This issue of favoritism in the aspect of appointment has impeded the effective condemnation of corruption incidents. To manage this issue, the government should take part in a more productive mass citizen mobilization for national integration that will promote patriotism among citizens if this approach is adopted, it will play an important role in reducing the threat of corruption. Every Nigerians will unite to reject all forms of corruptions. An example of how ethnic affiliation s can interfere with the fight against corruption can be drawn from the recent case of a former Minister of Aviation who got shelter and support from her eastern Nigerian colleagues.

METHODOLOGY

The study adopts a qualitative research approach and textual analysis. The argument in this study is that Nigeria continues to face significant challenges in her efforts to promote development for her citizens. Amidst various political, social, infrastructural, and existential related problems, there exists a wide gap that poses a significant threat to the nation's progress.

DISCUSSIONS AND FINDINGS

The findings of this study shows that Nigeria is struggling with an abundance of developmental challenges, raging form a lack of political will, weak leadership commitment, financing difficulties related to infrastructure development, insufficient public-private partnership teamwork, bribery and corruption, ineffective laws, insecurity, political instability, mismanagement of resources, economic recession amongst

others. The study provided a conceptual framework for understanding the notion of development and investigated the different barriers impeding Nigeria's development. It is obvious that Nigeria's defective change processes show a wide range of flawed values within its leadership, which is occasioned by either failure to prioritize the common good or to resort to complacency in the face of the harmful actions of a selected few. This corroborates Plato's submission that "the penalty that good (people) pay for not being interested in politics is to be governed by people worse than themselves". The right time for Nigerian political elites to assume greater responsibility is now. This will allow them take charge to avoid repetition of incompetence that has shaped the nation's political destiny.

Lack of sufficient accountability and transparency that is crucial for promoting good governance is one of the reasons for the failure of development programs in Nigeria. The only way through which Nigeria can consolidate its democratic achievement and effective administration is through accountability and openness. This will prepare Nigeria to capitalize on future international opportunities not only through reintegration in to the global economy. If these measures are put in place, they can help Nigeria's reputation to be restored, improve the local investment climate, and attract foreign investors to contribute to the nation's growth.

If the issues of corruption were to be effectively prevented in Nigeria, there should be improvement on the part of the country's law enforcement and anti-corruption institutions. This will help to address the high level of impunity that presently exists, and the government's lack of resolve in

combating corruption and the global breakdown of law and order. Corruption can also be tackled by establishing the rule of law and enhancing the judiciary system. If these measures are not taken into action, it will be very difficult to make progress in the fight against corruption, and many people will continue to act with impunity and appear to be immune to legal consequences.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This paper has discussed the obstacles to development in Nigeria. It recommended that the sections of the constitutions that allows public officials not to be punished even when there is evidence of wrongdoing should be expunged. In addition, state governors and local government chairmen and women access to allocated funds should be limited to avoid misuse of public resources. Appointment of leaders to lead Nigeria towards progress should be based on the meritorious official records, dedication to duty and unflinching believe in the Nigeria vision and mission. The government should focus on the establishment of policy consistency that will minimize the prevalence of abandoned projects.

Furthermore, a social safety net should be provided by the government to support the most disadvantaged members of the society. Also, a combination of strategies will assist these individuals regain their self-respect by providing them with meaningful employment opportunities In order to improve policy development and implementation, it is essential for the government to increase public participation. A bottom-up approach, which actively seeks inputs from citizens should be adopted by policy makers. This is made possible when comprehensive information about policy objectives, actions

taken and policies that will not be pursued through frequent public announcements are disseminated. The government must grant more operational freedom to specialized agencies (Economic and Financial Crime Commission and the Independent Corrupt Practices and other related offences commission) to combat corruption. Strict penalties should be given to whoever that is found guilty of proven offences.

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